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Resistance to market interventionism: an analysis of the European industrial carbon management strategy consultation

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ABSTRACT

Establishing a framework for carbon management in the European Union and aligning this with climate policy relies on collaboration between diverse actors and coordination between diverse goals. The European *Industrial Carbon Management Strategy*, a policy that sets ambitions for carbon capture, carbon utilization, carbon storage and carbon removals, was published in February 2024. The strategy underwent a public consultation during the summer of 2023. The consultation offered valuable insights on how the key stakeholders view the governance challenges. This study analyses the consultation submissions and how the stakeholders perceive carbon management challenges and solutions. All submissions ($n = 205$) to the call for evidence were synthesized using qualitative system dynamics modelling. The analysis resulted in the identification of two dominant approaches to carbon management, a market-driven and a society-driven approach, debated by the stakeholders. These two approaches have an inherent tension between them. The market-driven approach favours minimal regulation and relies on competition and economic incentives as key drivers for carbon management. In contrast, the society-driven approach advocates for strict regulation and active government intervention to ensure technology aligns with broader climate mitigation goals. The European industrial carbon management faces strong advocacy for a market-driven approach. However, due to the interconnections between decarbonization goals, inherent contradictions, and the collaborative nature of the challenge, a solely market-driven approach may not result in the desired acceleration.

Key policy insights

- Industry perspectives dominated the Industrial Carbon Management Strategy consultation, emphasizing economic effectiveness over other considerations.
- Focusing solely on economic effectiveness may not lead to the desired acceleration of carbon management.
- Sustainable carbon management deployment must also integrate environmental and societal considerations.
- Facilitating the participation of diverse societal actors supports the inclusion of environmental and societal considerations.

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1. Introduction

In February 2024, the European Union (EU) published the *Industrial Carbon Management Strategy* (European Commission, 2024), a policy that sets the ambitions for Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS), Carbon Capture and Utilisation (CCU) and carbon removals (Carbon Management technologies in the rest of the paper) in

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Europe. This study examines the public consultation process that the Strategy underwent in the summer of 2023. This study was undertaken before the publication of the Strategy and focuses on the consultation phase.

Policymakers at both European and national levels will face challenges in reconciling diverse perspectives, interests and carbon management pathways. Carbon management includes collaboration across the value chain and borders, making CO₂ infrastructure development a challenging undertaking. The EU Member States have different political attitudes towards carbon management (CCUS Forum, 2023b), and carbon capture projects have faced societal resistance (Ashworth et al., 2019; Pianta et al., 2021; Steeper, 2013). The decarbonization of industries relies on a combination of solutions such as CCUS, electrification, hydrogen and energy efficiency. These solutions require access to affordable clean energy, and are intertwined with decarbonization of transport, energy, waste management, and forestry and land use. The growth of carbon management technologies has been hindered by various barriers and societal resistance (Arranz, 2016; Metz et al., 2005). At the same time, carbon management is expected to provide a significant contribution to achieving climate targets (e.g. IEA, 2021).

Collaboration requires input from stakeholders to determine, and ultimately co-shape, problems and suitable solutions (Ansell & Gash, 2008; Kleanthis et al., 2022; Torfing & Ansell, 2017). In this paper, we analyse the submissions to the call for evidence¹ of the Strategy. The analysis of the submissions focuses on answering the following questions:

1. *What barriers and enablers are raised in the European Industrial Carbon Management Strategy call for evidence by the stakeholders?*
2. *Whose interests were presented throughout the consultation and how does this impact the results of the consultation?*
3. *How can insights from the consultation inform European carbon management governance?*

This study adopts qualitative system dynamics modelling (Meadows, 2008b) to analyse the diverse stakeholder perspectives. This approach helps to manage complex challenges by providing a way to understand them in the broader system context (see e.g. Janipour et al., 2021; Mirchi et al., 2012). The analysis identified two distinct approaches to carbon management: a market-driven approach and a society-driven approach. The market-driven approach prioritizes the acceleration of carbon management technologies as a standalone goal, while the society-driven approach views carbon management as a means to achieve the overarching goal of climate change mitigation. The approaches vary significantly with the desired level of control over the development of carbon management markets.

The next section of the paper discusses European industrial policy and public consultations. Section 3 will introduce the methods. Section 4 will discuss the results of the analysis through qualitative system dynamics diagrams. Section 5 will discuss the implications of the results. Lastly, Section 6 will conclude the paper.

2. Public consultations and European industrial policy

The European Commission uses consultations in policymaking to engage with diverse stakeholders and obtain approval and legitimacy for the policies (Labitzke, 2012; van Ballaert, 2017). The democratic credentials, legitimacy, and quality of the EU consultation regime have faced some scrutiny (Alemanno, 2020; Bunea, 2017; Frelüh-Larsen et al., 2023; Vasileiadou & Tuinstra, 2013). Policies similar to the Strategy, those aiming for soft law and recommendations, have been found to have a low diversity of consultation participants (Vasileiadou & Tuinstra, 2013). However, others argue that EU consultations alleviate bias between policy insiders and outsiders (Bunea, 2017). It is important to note that EU policy processes do not occur in a vacuum but rather in a complex context involving multiple levels, actors and both formal and informal processes (Wallace, 2005). Therefore, the consultation analysed in this paper is just one aspect of the policy process. It is also only a

¹https://ec.europa.eu/info/law/better-regulation/have-your-say/initiatives/13848-Industrial-carbon-management-carbon-capture-utilisation-and-storage-deployment/feedback_en?p_id=32161866 (accessed 30.10.2023).

part of the rapidly developing European carbon management framework and industrial policy. Annex 1 identifies policies that are part of the framework.

Tension between the freedom of the markets and the control of the direction of industries has characterized the development of European industrial policy (Mazzucato et al., 2015; McNamara, 2023; Pichler et al., 2021). Traditionally, the EU has taken a neoliberalist approach and focused on competition and openness of markets, putting significant trust in the ability of European markets to allocate resources, credit and production activity across the EU (McNamara, 2023). In recent years, the EU has been moving towards a more interventionist approach, driven by the green transition, global crises such as the COVID-19 pandemic and geopolitical instabilities (McNamara, 2023). This shift has included new policy rhetoric and stronger steering of industry development (McNamara, 2023). This steering has been guided by the pursuit of aspirational goals, such as environmental sustainability, and policies aiming towards economic competition and security (McNamara, 2023). Economic competitiveness is a long-standing goal of the EU, but this new shift has included an added emphasis on shielding the EU from global vulnerabilities (McNamara, 2023). Despite this shift, the European industrial decarbonization policy has faced critique over its tendency to defend economic growth and competitiveness over social and environmental considerations (Pichler et al., 2021).

European climate policy has faced challenges in developing cost-effective decarbonization (Böhringer, 2014). Many stakeholders argue that adopting a technology-neutral approach to policy is the most effective way to support cost-efficient decarbonization. However, EU policies tend to be more specific to certain technologies in practice (Azar & Sandén, 2011). Due to the political nature of the question, it would be more accurate to discuss how specific these policies should be (Azar & Sandén, 2011). A completely technology-neutral approach leaves much of the decision-making to the market, often overlooking societal considerations and failing to support promising but currently less profitable technologies (Azar & Sandén, 2011).

EU's carbon management framework development is gaining renewed momentum but facing critique due to the slow speed of development (CCUS Forum, 2023a). A limited inclusion of social considerations is particularly concerning as the current social sciences insights have not been adopted in practice (Buck, 2021) and the current discussions have had a strong acceptance focus, with limited attention given to other considerations such as justice (Swennenhuis et al., 2020; Upham et al., 2022), societal trust and participation (Otto et al., 2023; Porter et al., 2022; ter Mors & van Leeuwen, 2023). The importance of social acceptance has been recognized for carbon management as it has caused delays or even cancellations of projects (Ashworth et al., 2012; van Egmond & Hekkert, 2015). As the broader social sciences insights remain under-appreciated (Buck, 2021), this raises concerns that more societal barriers will emerge or that the societal impacts of carbon management may be left unrecognized.

3. Methodology

Qualitative system dynamics modelling is a method that focuses on the causal relationships between different variables (Meadows, 2008b). By mapping these relationships, the modelling provides insights into the submitters' reasoning and their assumptions about how the structure of the carbon management system influences its behaviour. The method helps to manage the complexity arising from multiple stakeholder perspectives by setting these perspectives in the broader system context (see e.g. Janipour et al., 2021; Mirchi et al., 2012). System dynamics modelling can help to identify leverage points where interventions can have a significant impact (Meadows, 2008a), thus contributing to effective decision-making.

For transparency, the models are accompanied by citations from the submissions following suggestions in the system dynamics literature (Jalali & Beaulieu, 2023; Turner, 2023) (see Annex 2 for example citations for each causal relationship). Interpretation is necessary to warrant fruitful analysis. Issues were only included in the models if multiple stakeholders brought them up and if their connection with other variables was explained. In some cases, various viewpoints were simplified into more straightforward relationships in the models, for example, when considering diverse citizen perspectives against carbon management technologies, which were summarized as concerns over the alignment of carbon management with broader decarbonization goals, as this was a core reason for the resistance.

The models follow system dynamics standards (Meadows, 2008b). Each arrow represents a causal relationship, an arrow from variable A to variable B means that A is the cause and that B is the consequence. A plus arrow in the model refers to a relationship where the variables move in the same direction, an increase (decrease) in A leads to an increase (decrease) in B. A minus arrow on the other hand means that the variables move in opposite directions, an increase (decrease) in variable A resulting in a decrease (increase) in variable B. If there is a closed circle of causal relationships this constitutes a feedback loop, where a change in a variable leads via the other variables to a further shift in that original variable. The feedback loops come in two forms. Reinforcing feedback loops amplify any change in the same direction, an initial increase (decrease) is followed by a further increase (decrease). Balancing loops dampen change because an initial increase (decrease) is followed by a change in the opposite direction, a decrease (increase). Reinforcing feedback loops are responsible for change and escalation while balancing feedback loops are responsible for stability and inertia. A delay is represented in the models with two lines in the middle of an arrow.

The analysis was carried out in three steps.

1. **Content analysis:** The first step included a content analysis of all the call for evidence submissions and identification of their key features. These key features included the name (when provided) and stakeholder category of the respondent, their key concerns, proposed solutions and presented knowledge statements.
2. **Identification of causal connections:** The second step focused on identifying causal connections between variables identified through the stakeholder arguments and the creation of qualitative system dynamic models based on this. In line with the system dynamics tradition, causal loop diagrams were used to map the causal mechanisms that were either explicitly mentioned in the submissions or implied in the reasoning. These causal diagrams help show visually which assumptions lead stakeholders to take certain viewpoints. The diagrams help to visually summarize and synthesize complex systems and worldviews.
3. **Literature reflection:** The third step of the analysis focused on reflecting on existing literature to identify and analyse the implications and gaps of the qualitative system dynamics models.

The approach adopted in the present study is similar to how the method has been adopted in other studies related to carbon management technologies (Janipour et al., 2021). The models are a representation of the mental models and beliefs of the actors who provided a submission to the consultation, and as such do not necessarily represent reality. They present how the key stakeholders perceive the system to operate and are influenced by personal biases.

4. Results

4.1. Key challenges raised by the stakeholders

The European Commission received 278 submissions to a pre-specified questionnaire (European Commission, 2023). For the call for evidence, they received 205 submissions. As the participants were able to give their feedback more freely to the call for evidence, this data is better suited for qualitative analysis.

Industry views prevailed in the consultation (European Commission, 2023) with approximately 65% of the submissions to the call for evidence coming from companies, businesses and business associations. NGOs and citizens each provided 20 submissions (9.8%). The 'others' category included 13 submissions (6.3%). Academic and research institutions (including think tanks) provided 8 submissions (3.9%). Public authorities provided 6 submissions (2.9%). Environmental organizations provided 3 submissions (1.5%), and trade unions provided 1 submission. The submissions raised various issues as obstacles to carbon management technology deployment, summarized in Table 1.

4.2. Market-driven and society-driven approaches

The analysis resulted in two distinct approaches to carbon management debated by the stakeholders: a market-driven approach and a society-driven approach. These approaches are best understood as a spectrum. The

Table 1. Key challenges and responsibilities.

Challenge	Raised often by	Relevant or Expected actor to take further action
Lack of a business case	Industry	Policymakers
Access to and development of transport and storage infrastructure	Industry and Civil Society Actors (NGOs, environmental organizations, citizens)	Industry and Policymakers
Limited attention to CCU compared to CCS	(CCU) industry	Policymakers
Overregulation	Industry	Policymakers
Lack of a clear regulatory framework	Industry, academic/research institutions, and NGOs	Policymakers
Responsibility/risk sharing	Industry	Industry and Policymakers
Lack of standardization	Industry, academic/research institutions and NGOs	Policymakers
Collaboration	A cross-cutting theme, raised by all stakeholder groups.	Everyone
Concern over the alignment of carbon management with broader decarbonization	Civil society actors and academic/research institutions	Policymakers
Concern over risks and societal costs	Civil society actors	Policymakers
Social acceptance	Industry and academic/research institutions	Policymakers (through awareness raising) and Society

market-driven approach generally sees regulation as an obstacle to technology deployment, and the society-driven approach sees interventions as a necessary condition to ensure that technology leads to desired results. The market-driven approach tends to reason with carbon management as the end goal in mind. The society-driven approach, on the other hand, reasons with climate change mitigation as the end goal, and carbon management as one of several pathways to achieve this goal. Figure 1 illustrates this difference.

A market-driven approach is a neoliberalist approach that favours free markets and technological neutrality. In this approach, the role of the EU is mainly restricted to enabling the market. The benefits of approaches that focus on economic considerations include cost-effectiveness and the ability to foster innovation (Sacchi et al., 2014; Sonneborn, 2004). Their weaknesses are seen to include the inability to create fundamental changes to the system, involve broad societal considerations, and decarbonize at the needed pace (Chaudhary, 2022; McNamara, 2023). Capitalist firms are believed to be unable to absorb the financial losses implied by a rapid transition to net zero (Adler, 2022). Market-driven approaches are also believed to be insufficient without policy support (Sonneborn, 2004).

Figure 1. The role of regulations differs between a market-driven (reasoning in blue) and a society-driven (reasoning in green) approach.

[redacted] asserts that authorities should not handpick winners and favour certain decarbonisation technologies. Instead, a level-playing field should be created where decarbonisation solutions can compete and offer the most cost-effective option for emitters. (Company/business submission)

A society-driven approach is an interventionist approach that focuses on careful steering of the market and carbon management through regulation. The integration of different climate mitigation goals and policies is at the core of the society-driven approach (Biesbroek, 2021; Meijers & Stead, 2004). Some examples of what this can look like include the times of imminent crises such as World War II (Adler, 2022) and the COVID-19 pandemic (Ansell et al., 2021; Scognamiglio et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2022). This type of approach requires democracy to ensure the legitimacy of the system, government support to incentivise innovation, and collective motivation (Adler, 2022). More fundamentally, a society-driven approach requires a move away from focus on cost-efficiency, as eco-efficiency is often not profitable (Adler, 2022). However, a society-driven approach can be considered too ambitious and costly, and public support in itself may not be enough to foster innovation and create enough incentive for industry participation.

– it is also important to ensure that a CO₂ storage target does not become an end goal in itself, risking the creation of perverse incentives and/or failing to encourage other means of decarbonization where possible (NGO submission)

The two approaches are best understood as a spectrum, with stakeholder perspectives positioned between them. Some trends in the perspectives raised by the stakeholders include industry actors advocating for a free-market approach, companies accepting regulations that don't negatively impact their business, NGOs and citizens questioning carbon management technologies, and diverse views from academic and research institutions and public authorities.

The submissions for the consultation mostly favoured a market-driven approach, influenced by industry dominance. The CCUS Forum also supports this approach, expressing concern about regulation hindering the market (CCUS Forum, 2023a). In summary, there is strong advocacy for a market-driven policy process. The upcoming sections will explore crucial aspects of carbon management in Europe, as outlined in the submissions.

4.3. The business case

4.3.1. The chicken-and-egg dilemma and the learning effect

The challenge of developing capture, transport, and storage capacity simultaneously was raised often in the submissions. The business case of both capture projects and transport and storage infrastructure projects relies on the existence of one another. Capture projects require the knowledge of where the CO₂ will be stored, how it will be transported there, and how much this will cost. Storage projects need a guarantee that they will have customers. CO₂ storage projects take a long time to develop, further complicating the challenge. Comparing this dilemma to the belief expressed in the submissions that the main challenge lies in getting projects started, as this will support further acceleration, emphasizes the dilemma as a flywheel effect: investment in one encourages investment in the other.

The submissions indicated a belief in the *learning effect* that further accelerates the positive reinforcing loop. Essentially, as more projects will be developed, the developers will learn from these, and the costs will decrease. The learning effect has impacted the acceleration of other technologies, such as renewables (de La Tour et al., 2013; Grafström & Poudineh, 2021). The strength of the learning effect depends on the technology and the causal mechanism can be more complex than that investment alone will lead to acceleration (Grafström & Poudineh, 2021). The learning effect for storage projects is expected to be lower than that of capture projects because storage projects take longer with fewer projects to learn from. The learning and flywheel effect beliefs underlined the market-driven approach and the concerns over overregulation stifling the market.

The flywheel effect of capture, transport and storage as well as the learning effects are visually summarized in Figure 2 below.

4.3.2. Belief in the market-driven approach

"EU Commission should choose a path wherethe best will not be the enemy of the good." (Business Association submission)

Figure 2. Flywheel and learning effects as the driving force of carbon management.

Concerns about over-regulation were common in the submissions, although some government interventions were deemed necessary, such as temporary public funding to decrease early mover risks and kick-start the market. To balance the existence of some interventions, many of the submissions called for streamlining of permitting processes. The submissions showcased a belief that the markets would become self-sufficient, leading to reduced public funding and lower overall cost and therefore greater societal benefit.

Uncertainty was another key challenge raised in the submission, which may negatively impact investor confidence and increase early-mover risks. This was followed by an emphasis that the role of the EU should

be to provide regulatory certainty. Some submissions argued that if the EU ETS price rises too much and there is no easy access to affordable carbon capture, European industries may relocate outside the EU, further enforcing the responsibility of the EU to provide a viable business case (see also CCUS Forum, 2023a).

4.3.3. CCU restrictions

Carbon utilization is one possible way to make carbon capture profitable. 58 of the submissions advocated for it to be given greater importance in European policy. These perspectives included the problematization of regulations that would hinder utilization, such as the hydrogen and renewable liquid and gaseous fuels of non-biological origin (RFNBO) regulations. Hydrogen can be combined with for example nitrogen or carbon to produce ammonia or synthetic hydrocarbons (Transport & Environment, 2023). This carbon could be recycled carbon derived through carbon capture, providing an incentive for carbon capture and utilization, but new regulations have put a 'sunset clause' for the use of carbon-based RFNBOs for 2041. The submissions argued that the increasing role of hydrogen and RFNBOs in decarbonization could be an avenue to support the business case for carbon utilization. Still, the European Commission's priority has been on renewable hydrogen.

The business case model in Figure 3 builds upon Figure 2 and adds the reasoning for greater focus on CCU.

4.4. Trade-offs of standardization

The development of a European-wide CO₂ infrastructure was raised as one of the key challenges for carbon management in Europe throughout the submissions. Initially, carbon capture projects relied on full-chain business models, but now, more diverse models are emerging with multiple actors and cross-border

Figure 3. Making a business case for carbon management.

Figure 4. Standardization helps international collaboration but reduces flexibility.

collaboration (IEA, 2023, p. 10). This cross-value chain and cross-border collaboration requires coordination and shared rules to prevent fragmented infrastructure development. The submissions raised important criteria for shared infrastructure including third-party access, transparency, standardization and clear shared rules among stakeholders (see also CCUS Forum, 2023c). Additionally, the submissions emphasized information sharing as a key challenge, prompting EU intervention. Some submissions discussed the option of exporting CO₂ for storage outside of the EU as a response to challenges with the ratification of the London Protocol.

Standardization was emphasized as a particularly pressing issue. What was missing in these discussions was the possible trade-off with decreased flexibility. As standards are set in place, it is harder to change them as technology develops. Flexibility is central to effective policymaking on complex challenges (Ansell et al., 2017). The importance of flexibility was recognized in the submissions but the impact standardization may have on it was not. This trade-off is illustrated in Figure 4.

4.5. Carbon management and broader decarbonization

The submissions that aligned with the society-driven approach emphasized that carbon management should be adopted only in cases where no other options to decarbonize are available (or economically feasible). Carbon management was recognized simultaneously as an essential solution to achieving net zero but also as a risk to deeper decarbonization as it may incentivise more fossil fuels or distract from other mitigation options. These perspectives emphasized the role of EU and Member State facilitation to ensure these risks are avoided.

The relationship between renewable energy and carbon capture is manyfold. Some of the submissions raised concerns that carbon management may take investment away from renewable energy technologies (see also Climate Action Tracker, 2023; van Egmond & Hekkert, 2012). However, other submissions emphasized that the underlying argument for carbon management relies on the accessibility of affordable clean energy and that with the increasing demand for clean energy, the supply may not meet the demand. Lastly, in some cases, the discussion on the availability of renewable energy was combined with a discussion on the intermittent nature of renewables to argue for coal power generation with carbon capture. The diverse perspectives on the relationship between carbon management and broader climate mitigation are illustrated in Figure 5.

As discussed in Section 4.3.3, some of the submissions problematized restrictions to carbon utilization as this would hinder the business case. Here we go back to that line of reasoning. Research from de Kleijne et al. (2022) has showcased that only CCU that stores emissions permanently or is made from zero-emissions energy is Paris

Figure 5. Carbon management and climate change mitigation risks.

Agreement compatible. The use of fossil fuel-based CCU for short-term products conflicts with climate change mitigation, as the emissions would be delayed (and only for short term) instead of avoided (Figure 6). On the other hand, the submissions advocating for limited restrictions for CCU underlined their argument with the reasoning that due to the continuous demand for carbon as a feedstock, if this carbon is not recycled, virgin fossil fuel resources will be used instead. This was connected to the argumentation that the supply from biogenic and atmospheric CCU would not be sufficient to meet the demand for carbon feedstock.

4.6. A reductionist understanding of the social considerations

The social considerations relevant for carbon capture were seen in a majority of the submissions in a reductionist way, the complexity of these issues reduced to a belief that lack of social acceptance is the core problem and that this can be mitigated through knowledge provision (Figure 7). Social scientists have attempted to bring more nuance into the discussion (Buck, 2021; de Coninck, 2013; Otto et al., 2023), but this nuance has not been adopted in practice. Moreover, social scientists have critiqued the deficit framing approach and assumptions that a lack of knowledge causes a lack of acceptance (Ahteensuu, 2012; Brunsting et al., 2013). The reductionist model is intertwined with the market-driven approach, as the legitimacy of this approach relies on diminishing the relevance of social issues. The industry perspectives on what are considered important societal considerations for carbon management are based on how they impact project development, emphasizing the responsibility of other actors to bring broader societal considerations into the discussions.

Out of 205 submissions, only 10 addressed social considerations beyond social acceptance and awareness, including topics such as trust, social costs, value sharing, engagement, public debate and justice. The C4U Horizon project was one of these submissions, and emphasized trust as a critical issue. This submission argued that societal trust and the justice of the transition are essential for the effective implementation of carbon capture technologies. The C4U project (Porter et al., 2022) underscores that societal support for CCUS is contingent on the perceived fairness of the transition and trustworthiness of the industry. The

Figure 6. Will strict regulation on carbon management lead to better alignment with broader decarbonization or will it lead to increased demand for virgin fossil resources?

government relies on the legitimacy of CCUS policies, which requires societal support (Porter et al., 2022). Industry places its importance on the business case (Porter et al., 2022). A key insight from their work is that carbon management implementation cannot be achieved without a broader understanding of societal considerations, as societal support, industry commitment and governmental action are strongly interrelated.

5. Discussion

The analysis of this paper resulted in the identification of two approaches to carbon management in Europe, a market-driven approach, and a society-driven approach. The submissions analysed for this study showcased a strong preference for the market-driven approach. A key difference between the two approaches is the extent of government intervention desired by the stakeholders. The market-driven approach is based on the belief that government interventions impede the emerging market. To speed up the deployment of carbon management, a technology-neutral approach and free competition should be embraced. The market-driven approach aligns with the traditional European neoliberalist market-making approach, and the society-driven approach aligns more closely with the recent interventionist approach guided by aspirational values (McNamara, 2023). The results of this study indicate a resistance towards a more interventionist approach to carbon management (cf. McNamara, 2023; Pichler et al., 2021).

As regulatory certainty and clear frameworks are key drivers of investment (IEA, 2023), collaboration requires shared rules and societal trust (Ansell & Gash, 2008), and government interventions are necessary to support emerging technologies which are not yet economically viable (McNamara, 2023), the desire for minimal interventions may not lead to the desired results. Focusing on the economic considerations may on the contrary lead to a slower pace and decreased depth of the transition instead of the aspired acceleration (Adler, 2022; Chaudhary,

Figure 7. A reductionist understanding of the social.

2022). The market-driven approach contains inherent contradictions, as it aims simultaneously for a technology-neutral approach, and wants minimal interventions but simultaneously market enablement and greater certainty. A key example of this discussion is the case of standardization, which is a form of government intervention but the lack of it was still problematized by the advocates of the market-driven approach. Similarly, stakeholders broadly recognized the need for government interventions to establish clear rules for collaboration, including access rights to infrastructure and cross-border transport. In other words, interventions were welcomed when they supported the goal of economic benefit and creating a business case for carbon management.

Many relevant decisions to carbon management are normative and require selection between diverse goals and values. The climate benefit of all carbon management pathways is not clear (de Kleijne et al., 2022; E3G & Bellona, 2023). The impact of different carbon management technologies and applications relies on the availability of clean energy and a full lifecycle assessment. A sustainable adoption of carbon management depends on diverse social, environmental and economic considerations (Covarrubias et al., 2024; Hardisty et al., 2011). With the market-driven approach, the decision-making would be left to economic considerations which are unlikely to fully cater to the interests of the wider society. Therefore, interventions are seen as key to achieving environmental and societal goals (Pichler et al., 2021). Still, economic incentives are key to motivating industries to participate in climate change mitigation. Therefore, a careful combination of the two approaches is recommended.

The perspective that social acceptance and awareness are the main or only relevant considerations was dominant in the submissions as well as in the broader CCUS discourse (CCUS Forum, 2023b). This reliance on the reductionist model poses a significant risk, as it may result in underestimating or ignoring social concerns. Introducing broader societal considerations into the discussion could shift the focus towards a society-driven approach and decrease uncertainty on the relationship between carbon management technologies and other decarbonization solutions. Market-driven approaches are less likely to result in a fair and inclusive transition (Rycroft et al., 2023). Ensuring inclusivity and a just transition is a key consideration at many levels of carbon management deployment in Europe. For one, the current developments have focused on North and West Europe, risking a scenario where East and South Europe are left behind.

6. Conclusions

This study analysed stakeholder submissions to the call for evidence for the European Industrial Carbon Management Strategy and identified two approaches to carbon management: a market-driven approach and a society-driven approach. Although the two approaches involve significant tension due to differing perspectives on government intervention, a balanced approach is recommended. As the policy processes face strong advocacy for a market-driven approach due to industry perspective dominance, this balancing act should focus on introducing broader societal considerations into the discussion. Sustainable carbon management requires equal inclusion of also societal and environmental considerations, which can be supported by enabling policy integration across diverse decarbonization goals and solutions, and involvement of diverse societal actors in carbon management debates.

As can already be seen with some national carbon management strategies, a more interventionist role can be undertaken by the Member States instead of the European Commission. This has been the case with the German carbon management approach, which includes steering the development through limiting public funding only to hard or impossible to abate emissions and prohibiting onshore storage (Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Climate Action, 2024). Moreover, the European Commission's approach in other decarbonization areas, such as with the focus on renewable hydrogen over other types of hydrogen production (European Commission, 2020), represents a more interventionist approach.

The consultation for the Industrial Carbon Management Strategy showcased a dominance of industry perspectives (the call for evidence 65.3%, the consultation 73%). A lack of diversity among participants in consultations for soft policy has been identified in previous studies (Vasileiadou & Tuinstra, 2013). The involvement of more diverse societal actors supports the inclusion of environmental and societal considerations (Vasileiadou & Tuinstra, 2013). Facilitating these broader considerations is therefore key to moving towards a society-driven approach. However, many societal actors have fewer resources and capacity to participate and are less experienced with maximizing their influence on the policy process through both formal and informal channels of participation. The idea expressed by industry stakeholders and advocates of carbon management is that it is time to shift from debating the necessity of carbon management technologies to taking action. However, research in the field of social sciences suggests that many decisions about carbon capture, such as their role in climate change mitigation, have not been openly discussed with the public (Otto & Gross, 2021). Facilitating a more diverse debate on carbon management requires capacity building of societal actors and catering of participation opportunities for more diverse participants.

The limitations of the study include the lack of direct stakeholder contact, which may have resulted in some considerations being left outside of the scope of the study. The selected method of system dynamics modelling also includes some limitations, the selection of variables always includes leaving some variables outside the scope of the study to make effective analysis possible. The lack of direct contact with the stakeholders was mitigated with extensive background work of the authors, including participation in the Commission events surrounding the consultation. Further research avenues highlighted by this study include carbon management collaboration practices, participation processes, and the balance between the two approaches in European Member State carbon management strategies and governments outside of Europe.

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Annex 1. European Carbon Management Framework

Document	Description
The Directive on the geological storage of CO ₂ (The CCS Directive) (European Commission, 2009)	The CCS Directive establishes a regulatory framework for the development and operation of geological carbon dioxide (CO ₂) storage in the EU.
The London Protocol	The London Protocol is an international treaty that regulates the disposal of products at sea, aiming to effectively control marine pollution. This includes CO ₂ streams. In 2009, the Protocol was amended to allow for cross-border transportation of CO ₂ for sub-seabed storage, but the amendment must be ratified by two thirds of the contracting parties to enter into force, and this has not yet taken place. A further resolution in 2019, allowed for a provisional adoption of the 2009 amendment before it comes into force. Two or more countries can now agree to transport CO ₂ for sub-seabed geological storage.
The Green Deal Industrial Plan (2023) (Commission, 2023)	The Green Deal Industrial Plan was published in February 2023, and it sets ambitions for the green transition of Europe's industry. The plan identifies carbon capture technologies as one of the solutions to achieve climate neutrality.
EU Green Deal	The European Green Deal, approved in 2020, is a set of policy initiatives by the European Commission with the overarching aim of making the European Union climate neutral in 2050.
The Net-Zero Industry Act	The European Commission proposed the Net-Zero Industry Act on 16 March 2023. The Act is part of the Green Deal Industrial Plan and its goal is to provide a predictable and simplified regulatory environment. The Act promotes investment in net-zero technologies, such as carbon management technologies. The Act is one of the measures introduced to help deliver on the goals of the Fit For 55 and REPowerEU objectives. REPowerEU is a European Commission proposal to end reliance on Russian fossil fuels before 2030 in response to the 2022 Russian invasion of Ukraine.
Fit For 55 legislative package	Under the European Climate Law, the EU has committed to reduce its net greenhouse gas emissions by at least 55% by 2030. The Fit for 55 package aims to make all sectors of the EU's economy fit to meet this target. As a part of this legislative package, the EU Emissions Trading System (ETS) has been reformed.
The EU Emissions Trading System (ETS)	The EU ETS is the EU's carbon emissions trading scheme which began in 2005. It works on a 'cap and trade' principle. Emitters are given emission allowances, which decrease over time, aligning with climate goals. If the emitters emit more than their allowances permit, they must buy more allowances on the EU Carbon Market or through trading with other companies or pay fines.
EU Strategy on Energy System Integration	The EU strategy on energy system integration aims at linking the various energy carriers, electricity, heat, cold, gas, solid and liquid fuels, with each other and with the end-use sectors, such as building, transport or industry. This linking-up also includes CO ₂ infrastructure.
Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism	The Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism is a carbon tariff on carbon-intensive products, such as cement and some electricity, imported by the European Union. The mechanism takes effect in 2026.

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Relationship	Citation example
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The strictness of regulation → (+) the harmonization of climate change mitigation approaches The harmonization of climate change mitigation approaches → (+) climate change mitigation (Mt avoided/year) 	<p><i>'While of crucial importance, CCS is no silver bullet. [redacted] targeted use is key.'</i>(NGO submission)</p> <p><i>'[redacted] would again like to repeat that the different potential for climate impacts from CCS and CCU, with the latter's climate impact being highly variable. This must be taken into consideration when determining where the public's support and where funding is best placed to foster market development in a manner consistent with the climate crisis.'</i> (NGO submission)</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The strictness of regulation → (–) carbon capture (Mt/year) 	<p><i>'However, The CO₂ market is still at a very early stage and as such does not require a full fledged regulatory framework beyond what is already provided in the CCS directive.'</i> (Company/Business submission)</p> <p><i>'[redacted] stresses the need to align current EU-legislation (e.g. on nature) with our common challenge for a swift decarbonization of our economies, allowing large-scale CCS projects to be realized swiftly in the EU (for example by granting certain exemptions in permitting procedures for net-zero technologies as CCS).'</i> (Company/business submission)</p> <p><i>'We cannot afford to be ideological about technologies and their use; the earlier CCS technologies start being deployed at scale, the faster we will start storing large quantities of emissions and reducing costs. That is why CCS-related policies should aim at facilitating investments and at helping CCS become an option for decarbonization, rather than restricting beforehand its use and room for deployment.'</i>(Company/business submission)</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Carbon capture → (+) climate change mitigation (Mt avoided/year) Carbon capture projects → (+) CO₂ mitigation Emissions → (–) climate change mitigation (Mt avoided/year) 	<p><i>'The science is clear that carbon dioxide removal (CDR) – alongside a strong prioritization on greenhouse gas emissions reduction – is 'unavoidable,' and will be required at gigatonne (Gt) global scale by 2050 to reach net zero and have a chance to limit warming to 1.5 or even 2°C.'</i> (Business association submission)</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The attractiveness of transport and storage of CO₂ → (+) investment in transport and storage capacity Investment in transport and storage capacity → (+) transport and storage capacity Transport and storage capacity → (+) the attractiveness of capturing CO₂ The attractiveness of capturing CO₂ → (+) investments in capture capacity Capture capacity → (+)the attractiveness of transport and storage of CO₂ 	<p><i>'As noted by the [redacted], accelerating CCUS is a 'chicken and egg' problem. Transport and storage operators will not invest unless they have binding CO₂ volumes from emitters, who in turn will not invest in capture technology without access to transport and storage.'</i> (Other category submission)</p> <p><i>'The main barrier to CCS development is first and foremost the lack of available CO₂ storage and transport infrastructure, which in turn discourage investments in carbon capture technologies.'</i> (Company/business submission)</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cost reduction transport and storage through learning → (–) cost of transport and storage Transport and storage capacity → (+) experience with transport and storage Cost reduction capture through learning → (–) the cost of capture Capture capacity → (+) experience with capture Experience with capture → (+) cost reduction capture through learning Investments in capture capacity → (+) capture capacity 	<p><i>'As a ready to scale-up technology, public support through provision of incentives and development of robust regulatory frameworks could allow corporates to claim removals and further catalyse financing for the accelerated deployment of the technology, thereby stimulating cost reductions associated with economies of scale.'</i> (Company/business submission)</p> <p><i>'That is why, at first, Europe should focus on supporting those projects that can be deployed faster and more cost-efficiently – which will depend largely on location and various technical factors – so that they can pave the way for cost reduction, infrastructure build-up and scale-up of the technology. Once those low-hanging fruits have been picked and costs reduced, it will be easier to apply CCS to those industries for which it is harder to do so today.'</i> (Company/business submission)</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The cost of capture → (–) business case The cost of transport and storage → (–) the attractiveness of transport and storage of CO₂ The cost of capture → (–) the attractiveness of capturing CO₂ 	<p><i>'CCS has the potential to be a great decarbonisation solution for Europe while protecting its industry and preserving jobs; but for CCS to be able to be deployed at scale, costs need to be brought down.'</i> (Company/business submission)</p>

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Relationship	Citation example
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The attractiveness of capturing CO₂ → (–) companies moving outside of the EU Companies moving outside of the EU → (–) climate change mitigation 	<p><i>'For Europe to remain on track to its climate objectives, while preserving the competitiveness of its industry, a marked shift in approach is needed towards more technology-inclusive, competitiveness-oriented, and less prescriptive policymaking.'</i> (Business Association Submission)</p> <p><i>'Certain industries, e.g. cement, lime, steel, or glass production, emit CO₂ not related to the combustion of fossil energy. CCUS is the key solution to mitigate process related emission from these industries allowing them to continue operating in the EU.'</i> (Business Association submission)</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Restrictions on the use of fossil fuel based carbon utilization → (–) demand for CCU products Demand for CCU products → (+) the attractiveness of carbon utilization CCU → (+) business case for carbon capture projects The attractiveness of carbon utilization → (+) the attractiveness of capturing CO₂ 	<p><i>'It is imperative to assess precisely what would be the impacts of a general sunset clause for the use of industrial CO₂ in 2040. In France, and probably in the rest of Europe, the major entries into service for production projects of synthesis molecules are planned in 2027–2028. These projects need to work at least 15 years, rather 20 years, to amortize their investments. Therefore, a sunset clause on December 31, 2040, is just equal to stop immediately the investment decisions and to block the projects.'</i> (Business association submission)</p> <p><i>'The current EU framework endangers ongoing and planned CCU investments. For instance, the decision to no longer consider CO₂ emissions put to use in Renewable Fuels of Non-Biological Origin (RFNBO) as being avoided from 2041 is not justified and should urgently be reviewed. These rules result in cutting off a CO₂ supply without assessment of the availability of CO₂ from biogenic sources and DAC to respond into the CO₂ industrial needs.'</i> (Business association submission)</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The strictness of carbon management regulations → (–) the attractiveness of capturing CO₂ 	<p><i>'To maximize their value, carbon management solutions should not be envisaged only as a last resort to mitigate residual industrial emissions; but also, as an efficient solution to reduce other sectoral emissions, decarbonize flexible power generation, enable the production of low-carbon hydrogen needed to fuel the industries of tomorrow, and to achieve negative emissions when combined for instance with bioenergy.'</i>(Company/business submission)</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The strictness of carbon management regulations → (+) climate change mitigation 	<p><i>'The ICMS should treat CCS on its own as a transitional means of addressing emissions from certain industrial activities to be used in certain cases. There are certain instances when CCS can have significant greenhouse gas mitigation potential and can be integrated into existing industrial processes and activities, whilst avoiding significant negative side effects and fossil fuel lock in.'</i> (NGO submission)</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The strictness of carbon management regulations → (–) investor confidence 	<p><i>'The certification process needs to be technology neutral and open for all carbon removal options available to ensure that no viable solution is excluded. Under the current proposed definitions, it is unclear whether capture and storage of the biogenic CO₂ from waste-to-energy would be eligible.'</i> (Company/business submission)</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EU ETS price (+) business case 	<p><i>'However, rising carbon prices including ETS, lower technology costs and the development of a mature CCS market, are likely to lead to a balance between ETS cost savings and the costs of CCS-gained CO₂ reductions. At least for emitters whose emissions are all part of the ETS system.'</i> (Public authority submission)</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Temporary public funding to initiate the market → (–) the cost of capture Temporary public funding to initiate the market → (–) uncertainty 	<p><i>'In the initial phase, public funding, coupled with coordinated infrastructure planning, will be necessary for the development of CO₂ transport and storage infrastructure, while de-risking policies will be crucial to empower private players to kickstart the deployment of CCS.'</i> (Company/business submission)</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Uncertainty → (+) early mover risk Early mover risk → (–) investor confidence Investor confidence → (+) business case Risk reduction → (+) business case 	<p><i>'In that sense, the development of a regulatory framework for Carbon transport and storage faces a number of the challenges that e.g. the roll-out of next generation fibre networks and hydrogen networks have also faced recently in that regulators need to provide a framework that incentivises the build-out of new infrastructure in the presence of volume risk, which in this case can be understood as</i></p>

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Relationship	Citation example
	<i>uncertainty about the overall economic viability of the infrastructure (as opposed to year-on-year demand fluctuations).’ (Company/business submission)</i>
	<i>‘Current ETS prices are not sufficient to drive the not-yet established CCS value chain. This means that first movers in any part of the value chain will need to take disproportionate risks.’ (Public authority submission)</i>
	<i>‘It also refers to enabling and introducing barrier-reducing policy instruments, which the European Commission’s Industrial Carbon Management initiative can facilitate to create the requisite ambitious conditions to reduce project risk through clarity and regulatory certainty, which will drive projects towards implementation. This is why Aker Carbon Capture first and foremost, calls for support and incentives that rewards actors who move first to decarbonize.’ (Company/business submission)</i>
• Standardization and interoperability → (+) transparency	<i>‘A robust and consistent GHG accounting is necessary to avoid gaps and double counting. In order to promote innovation towards avoiding emissions and even removing CO₂ from the atmosphere, there should be clear rules on monitoring and accounting in ETS and non-ETS sectors. The objectives should be that all CO₂ is accounted for, including transfers and that double counting and/or double crediting is avoided.’ (Company/business submission)</i>
• Transparency → (+) effective coordination	<i>‘In addition to CO₂ capture and storage activities, Member States should be obliged to provide information on national and international transport needs and activities to assist in coordinating ‘source – sink’ matching across the Union and third countries.’ (Company/business submission)</i>
• Effective coordination → (+) collaboration between countries	<i>‘Although various EU member states have already signed MoUs on cross-border transport (like the Netherlands and Belgium), [redacted] sees an active role for the European Commission as well in improving the legal and policy frameworks for cross-border CO₂-transport and promoting cross – border cooperation.’ (Company/business submission)</i>
• Collaboration between countries → (+) cross-border infrastructure	<i>‘Furthermore, we encourage the EU and its Member states to collaborate closely to align as far as possible the requirements for financial security site operators must provide across Europe as well as the regulatory framework for handover of liability of stored CO₂.’ (research submission)/research submission)</i>
• Cross-border infrastructure → (+) CO ₂ mitigation	<i>‘The future of an efficient low carbon economy relies on the development of CO₂ infrastructure networks.’ (Company/business submission)</i>
• Standardization and interoperability → (+) providing certainty and predictability	<i>‘More clarity on the rules would significantly help to accelerate the development and use of CO₂ storage in Europe. The ICMS could also introduce a regime of CO₂ transport and storage go to areas to help speed up the permitting process in individual member states or as part of cross border projects.’ (NGO submission)</i>
• Providing certainty and predictability → (+) risk reduction	<i>‘This creates a different set of challenges, as this shared infrastructure will need to aggregate multiple CO₂ sources and end-uses (whether utilisation or storage), which requires harmonised specifications and standards, as well as a robust model for sharing risks and liabilities, which should not fall solely on the public sector.’ (Academic/research submission)</i>
• Business case → (+) carbon capture projects	<i>(one of two main challenges to carbon capture technologies): ‘Lack of market mechanism: Legal security is needed to encourage investments in CCUS technologies, but an adequate policy framework is currently missing.’ (Company/business submission)</i>
• Business case → (+) the attractiveness of capturing CO ₂	
• Effective policies → (+) CO ₂ mitigation	<i>‘Developing an integrated and coherent EU strategy for CCUS through a decentralized principle – the strategy should address elements relevant to cross border (standards, quality, and trade) while allowing flexibility for Member States to develop national strategies, markets, and structures.’ (Public authority submission)</i>

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Relationship	Citation example
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Investment in carbon management technologies → (–) investment in other mitigation options Investment in other mitigation options → (+) climate change mitigation (Mt avoided/ year) Investment in other mitigation options → (+) the share of renewable energy in the system Low regulation carbon management (e-fuels, other short lifetime CCU products, fossil sources of carbon) → replacement of renewables or other more sustainable options 	<p><i>'In 2009, we created a website dedicated to CCS, where we analysed a wide range of issues related to CCS: timing (in the climate context), environmental impacts, climate impacts, economics, financing, liability, relationship to energy scenarios and CDM/JI, among others. These analyses led us to conclude that CCS could not be considered a viable climate tool, but rather a tool of interest to the coal, oil and gas industry and the energy companies – and countries – with large fossil fuel interests.'</i> (NGO submission)</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The share of renewable energy in the system → (+) the intermittency of energy supply The intermittency of energy supply → (+) investment in energy generation from fossil fuels with carbon capture 	<p><i>'In the lead up to 2030 we should invest in all the green technologies such as solar panel production, wind turbines and renewable hydrogen for targeted sectors to reach the 2030 climate goals. CCS cannot and should not be put on equal footing with existing alternatives already proven to significantly cut carbon emissions and phase out fossil fuels.'</i> (NGO submission)</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Investment in energy generation from fossil fuels with carbon capture → (–) climate change mitigation (Mt avoided/year) 	<p><i>(CCS is required to ...): 'complement the role played by renewable technologies in the power sector, by introducing in the power mix a clean dispatchable energy resource able to maintain the adequacy and the reliability in a decarbonized electricity system'</i> (company/business)</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The attractiveness of carbon utilization → (+) CCU 	<p><i>'For instance, CO₂ streams captured from fossil fuel sources or whose technologies depend on the continued use of fossil fuels will undermine the decarbonisation potential that these technologies represent for the sector.'</i> (Company/business submission)</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Short lifetime carbon products → (+) the attractiveness of carbon utilization 	<p><i>'Companies with industrial CO₂ sources are not supported today to install carbon capture plants dedicated to CCU because CCU (except for CO₂ permanently bound by mineralization) is not accepted as emission abatement in the ETS. When the resulting CCU product is not accepted as "green" or "sustainable" without a sunset clause even if required CO₂ certificates are submitted, it is unlikely that a CCU company will pay for the CO₂. Therefore, investments in CCU value chains are not incentivized today, even though they could lead to an overall CO₂ reduction in the short term.'</i> (Other category submission)</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Short lifetime carbon products → (+) emissions 	<p><i>'Carbon is an important component in many products, and today most of that carbon comes from fossil sources. There is, however, not enough non-fossil carbon available for companies and other stakeholders to use in their production, as a result of the lack of investment in CCUS technology and the lack of a well-functioning transportation network for captured CO₂. Favourable conditions and rules could facilitate and accelerate the development of new CCUS technologies, which could help to mitigate emissions and contribute to more sustainable production of carbon-based products.'</i> (Company/business submission)</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Restrictions on the use of fossil fuel based carbon capture and utilization → (+) the use of virgin fossil resources The use of virgin fossil resources → (+) emissions Low regulation carbon management (e-fuels, other short lifetime CCU products, fossil sources of carbon) → the replacement of virgin fossil fuels with recycled carbon and e-fuels 	<p><i>'Carbon removals will play an indispensable part in reaching the EU's climate neutrality goal for 2050. Hence it is urgent that carbon is supported by an appropriate policy framework that needs to be developed. At the same time, achieving negative CO₂ emissions by carbon removals must not in any way replace or reduce the efforts to mitigate emissions by phasing out fossil fuels.'</i> (Business association submission)</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The strictness of regulation → (–) low regulation carbon management (e-fuels, other short lifetime CCU products, fossil sources of carbon) The carbon lifetime of CCUS → (+) climate change mitigation 	<p><i>'Being aware that only a limited and insufficient amount of renewable energy as well as renewable hydrogen is available it should be noticed that with this limited amount of renewable energy and renewable hydrogen more fossil based chemicals and fuels can be replaced by using CO-containing process gases compared to CO₂ based processes.'</i> (Other category submission)</p>
	<p><i>'When using CO₂ capture and utilisation (CCU), i.e. the use of new fuels and materials, it must be ensured that carbon dioxide is not released back into the atmosphere, even after ideally repeated use. CCU should</i></p>

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Relationship	Citation example
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CCU in low lifecycle products → (-) carbon lifetime of CCUS • Restrictions on the use of fossil fuel based carbon utilization → (-) CCU in low lifecycle products 	<p><i>therefore be limited to the use of CO₂ from the air.'</i> (translated from Germany, NGO submission)</p> <p><i>'Once the carbon is captured, a long-term storage must be guaranteed by permanently storing carbon in geological formations. The conversion of carbon to products with a short lifetime, such as e-fuels, should not be accounted for.'</i> (NGO submission)</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The strictness of regulation → (+) strict carbon management (permanent storage, biogenic and atmospheric sources of carbon) 	<p><i>'It is important to envisage CCS only after the other options have been considered, not as a default. CCS should not delay the urgent need to reduce emissions at the source. For certain industrial sectors other options are now available. This will maintain the incentive to reduce emissions at the source over end-of-pipe technologies.'</i> (NGO submission)</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strict carbon management (permanent storage, biogenic and atmospheric sources of carbon) → Climate change mitigation (Mt avoided/year) 	<p><i>'The overarching goal of the energy and climate policy should be to reduce greenhouse gas emissions. Thus, the CCUS strategy should outline policies and support mechanisms that allow the use of CCUS only in the case of emissions that are impossible or economically unprofitable to avoid, so that the possibility of installing CCUS does not provide an incentive, e.g. to build new generation capacities based on fossil fuels.'</i> (Academic/research submission)</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Awareness raising campaigns → (+) public awareness • Carbon management in Europe → (+) public awareness 	<p><i>'Improving social acceptance of CCS projects will require more efforts from EU and MSs in disseminating and sharing information, including technical ones, on CCS needed role in the decarbonization process.'</i> (Company/business submission)</p> <p><i>Implied that familiarity will increase awareness.</i></p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public awareness → (+) the social acceptance of carbon management technologies 	<p><i>'To what extent the much needed public support will be awarded to CCS projects in the long-term, in a predictable manner reducing investment risks and foster market development, depend on public support and awareness of the technology.'</i>(NGO submission)</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The social acceptance of carbon management technologies → (+) carbon management in Europe 	<p><i>'Derisking also means that the upcoming CCUS strategy should pivotally address public awareness and acceptance – this is crucial in the development of CCUS projects in territories.'</i> (Company/business submission)</p>